

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D3.1 Handheld Sensor Prototype

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ACRONYMS LIST

TMF	Trace My Fish
R&D	Research and Development
UX	User Experience
ICT	Information and Communications Technologies
API	Application Programming Interface
SSO	Single Sign On
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
GUI	Graphical User Interface
AI	Artificial Intelligence

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The following deliverable aims at giving an overview of the planning and development process for the Videometer handheld instrument: the VideometerLite. The device, together with the image processing software, the VideometerLab Software, have been utilized, and further will, during the whole duration of the TraceMyFish (TMF) project for the gathering, processing, and analyzing of data.

After an initial introduction to Workpackage 3, the second Chapter of the Deliverable gives a detailed introduction to the Videometer Spectral Imaging technology and to the software's functionalities and tools.

Chapter 3 revolves around the instrument's concept of a portable, wireless, easy-to-use device. Chapter 4 and 5 further develop this notion, respectively expanding on the iterative process undertaken for the design of the device, and the first iteration of the development process. To satisfy customer needs as efficiently as possible, it was necessary to create a cross-functional team of developers, including mechanics, optics, hardware and software engineers, marketing specialists, executives and the users themselves.

The 6th Chapter of the Deliverable focuses on user testing and the feedback received after the first iteration of the design process. Users were overall satisfied with the instrument and showed the need for further expansion of UV wavelengths. Chapter 7, indeed, depicts how the user's input drove the second iteration of the instrument's design process. Additional wavelengths were added, and the Videometer Cloud Workspaces were developed for the saving, managing and sharing of data.

Finally, Chapter 8 serves as a manual for the use of the instrument, software and cloud integration as a unique system, that allows for advanced image capturing, processing and analysis. Tools such as the transformation builder, segmentation builder, BLOB tool and Cloud Workspace give the user the unique possibility for combining spectral imaging, machine learning, multivariate statistics with their product's needs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aiming at advancing the seafood industry with technologies that ensure full traceability, safety, and quality of aquatic products, TraceMyFish' Task 3.1 has focused on the development of a portable, easy-to-use, and cost-efficient sensor, the VideometerLite instrument, and its integration with the VideometerLab software and Videometer Cloud Workspaces.

The task was carried out in-between Month 1 (November 2021) and Month 15 (January 2022) of the project and was performed by partners Agricultural University of Athens, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, University of Iceland, Matis and Videometer A/S. The universities and research institution, Matis, focused on the testing of the portable instrument, while Videometer's role was that of designing and developing the device itself, integrating software, and the Cloud Workspaces.

2 VIDEOMETER'S SPECTRAL IMAGING TECHNOLOGY

The portable instrument is based on Videometer's spectral imaging technology. Spectral imaging is a scientific methodology which combines imaging with spectroscopy, allowing for the measurement of different spectra within the same image (Carstensen, 2018)

Spectral imaging, in the Videometer case, is achieved by placing a camera on the top of an integrating sphere, with LEDs of different wavelengths placed around its equator. The integrating sphere comprises of a hollow sphere with a highly reflective coating, which allows for uniformity in the scattering and diffusing effects of the LEDs' light rays (Figure 1). The LEDs strobe sequentially to capture a stack of images recorded at different wavelengths. Consequently, each pixel in the captured image represents a reflectance spectrum. The range of the Videometer technology includes ultraviolet, visual, and near-infrared wavelengths. Additionally, fluorescence can be captured by placing different filters in front of the camera. (Carstensen & Folm-Hansen, 2006).

Videometer's flagship instrument, the VideometerLab (Figure 1), captures images with up to 20 different wavelengths ranging from 365 nm to 970 nm. The VideometerLite (Figure 2) instrument, on the other hand, is developed to capture images with an array of 12 wavelengths ranging between 365 nm to 850 nm.

Figure 1 VideometerLab

Figure 2 VideometerLite

Videometer's technology further develops on its spectral imaging methodology by combining it with a machine learning, AI, and cloud-driven software for accurate and comprehensive analysis of the images taken. Both instruments come with the VideometerLab Software (Figure 3), which, besides offering image visualization, allows the user to perform advanced image analysis and processing. Among others, the platform implements algorithms for transforming and segmenting images, for automatic recognition of sample features and for

model building. The VideometerLab Software includes the Videometer Cloud Workspaces, virtual locations which allow the users to store, manage and share their data with their stakeholders.

In order to design the instrument and software with the user at mind, an iterative, agile process was setup. The following sections of deliverable will expand on the conceptualization, design and manufacturing process, and,

Figure 3 VideometerLab Software – Transformation Builder and Segmentation Builder 2. Seabrim image kindly provided by Agricultural University of Athens

additionally, on the use, applications and future developments of the full system.

3 PROCESS

Successful product development begins with the users and is driven by the attempt to solve their needs in the most functional and innovative way possible. For this reason, it is crucial to plan an iterative conceptualization and design process that involves the users as sources of ideas and evaluation. The process is described in Figure 4.

Lead users from the partnered Universities and from the seafood industry were consulted, as their extensive knowledge provided insights in the practical use of the instrument and in application areas such as microbiology, food science, hazard detection, supply chain processes, methodologies, and tools.

Figure 4 VideometerLite Design and Development Iterative Process

To further ensure a comprehensive plan, the VideometerLite design process involved cross-functional teams with expertise in different areas. Videometer's team included product developers, software developers, mechanical, electronics and photonics engineers, marketing specialists and executive management members. Each function focused on different aspects of the product's development and meetings were held to coordinate the work and plan for next steps.

It should be noted that the VideometerLite and Cloud Workspaces development process begun previously to the start of the TraceMyFish project. This meant that a portion of the planning and implementation of the system had already been achieved before November 2021. Thus, the design process was further supplemented by the insights deriving by the TraceMyFish consortium.

4 VIDEOMETERLITE CONCEPT

Because the TraceMyFish project focuses on safety and quality insurance throughout the seafood value chain, it was crucial to design an instrument that allows for flexibility for each node of the network. **Task 2.1 - Elicitation of bluebio value chains and actor's needs**, and **8.1 - Market analysis, positioning, and uptake strategy**, identified different user scenarios by interviewing stakeholders in different milieus. The findings of the two tasks, demonstrated the need for an instrument which could be used in the following settings:

- In laboratory (R&D)
- Industrial setting (at-line)
- In-field (retailer)
- In-field (harvesting)

Furthermore, **Task 8.1 – Market analysis, positioning and uptake strategy** brought to light the four main user personas that would be utilizing the instrument for their analysis. The personas are:

- Researchers and R&D professionals
- Food processors
- Harvesters
- Retailers

Their use of the instrument is varied and dependent on different needs, however several commonalities are present in their feature specifications. First and foremost, is the need of an instrument that can be carried to the different environments that shape the industry. Second, and connected to portability, is the crucial feature of wirelessness. The absence of cables, in fact, allows for the instrument to be portable and easy-to-manage. The VideometerLite is intended to be cost-efficient, to be affordable by users in different stages of the value chain. This means that the product should be designed and manufactured taking into consideration profit margins in relation to costs. Finally, the instrument is designed to be easy-to-use allowing all different user personas to perform their required analysis without the need for extended training, nor the incurrance of obstructions in their workflow.

At the same time, the VideometerLite device had to reflect the above-mentioned LED-based spectral imaging technology that characterizes its parent-product: the VideometerLab.

Based on these features a product concept statement was formulated as follows:

“A new handheld spectral imaging device, which can in a user-friendly, reliable and cost-efficient way detect and monitor hazards, malpractices and adulteration throughout the seafood value chain.”

5 FIRST ITERATION IN THE DESIGN PROCESS

Once the concept statement of the VideometerLite had been identified, the first iteration of the design process was commenced.

With spectral imaging being the core technology of the VideometerLite, and portability and wirelessness being the main features, the first prototype iteration consisted in the design of the system critical properties needed for the functioning of the system. The essential optics, electronics and mechanics were investigated and prototyped in this stage.

5.1 HARDWARE, OPTICS AND MECHANICS

First and foremost, portability implied a smaller and lighter integrating sphere with a diameter of 130 mm, which can easily be managed in different environments. Because of the size of the sphere, it was decided that the instrument should capture images in 7 wavelengths in the spectrum of 405-850 nm i.e., 405 nm, 460 nm, 525 nm, 590 nm, 621 nm, 660 nm, and 850 nm. These wavelengths were chosen for their cost/efficiency ratio, while having a sufficient cover of the visible range and inclusion of UV and NIR wavelengths.

Moreover, the size of the sphere and the number and range of wavelengths required that the optical structure of the camera and LEDs had to be designed so it could fit the equator's surface. This meant that the LEDs' structure had to be designed for an optimal ratio of defused light versus sphere size, while still performing accurate measurements.

In regard to the electronic components of the instrument, the first iteration examined the necessary circuits for the operational activity of the VideometerLite prototype. A breadboard base was used to build the first semi-permanent prototype of the device. The base served as a rapid mean of modular implementation of the electronic development.

Some initial considerations were made for the cost-efficiency of the VideometerLite, regarding materials and methods of production, in order to keep the cost of production to a set level.

This initial prototype was tested and proofed by product developers with experience within electronics, mechanic and optical design, as their knowledge and experience in the field allowed the assessment of its functionality.

Once the first prototype was tested, its electronics were refined and expanded so to be able to function with the 7 chosen wavelengths. With the electrical circuits defined, it was necessary to develop a custom Printed Circuit Board (PCB), which could enable the device to be packed in a compact, portable shell.

The mechanic design was enhanced to be more ergonomic and cost-efficient. The instrument was made lighter and more manageable. The ergonomic design included the development of two buttons at hands-reach: one for booting the instrument up, and the other to capture images and calibrate the VideometerLite.

5.2 SOFTWARE (ICT)

Initial software connection development focused on the integration of the VideometerLite prototype with a simple RESTful (Representational State Transfer) API. The VideometerLite's RESTful API allowed the instrument to be controlled and supervised via Wi-Fi and ethernet connection from a computer.

5.3 SOFTWARE (IMAGE ANALYSIS AND PROCESSING)

The integration between the VideometerLab software and the VideometerLite instrument was extended with intuitive functions, tools and buttons to allow connectivity, image-capturing and analysis. Additionally, optimization in the software API happened in terms of speed, allowing image capturing to happen in a matter of 7-10 seconds. The interface was expanded with optimized image-capturing time, to allow for more rapid in-field analysis and motion-control.

5.4 SOFTWARE (INTERACTION DESIGN)

Cloud infrastructure was planned and developed during this first iteration. Initial integration included the possibility to log into the MyVideometer system through single sign on (SSO). A plan was identified in regard to how to save, access and share data on the Videometer Cloud workspaces so that all resources could be available with one login system.

5.5 USERS

The wavelengths necessary for the seafood applications were investigated, both by interviewing the TraceMyFish partners and stakeholders, and by performing some in-house tests.

Partners were interviewed in relation to their needs and use of the VideometerLite. Semi-structured interviews were followed, in order to leave space for communication, and to avoid any possible bias by the interviewees. Here, they were asked what their intended use of the VideometerLite would be and which applications would be more suitable for the value chain they operate in.

Appendix 11.1 shows the interview template that was used for the gathering of data. Note that not all questions were asked, and this template was utilized as a guide for topics to be touched upon during the conversations: Participants from the TraceMyFish Consortium included:

- Dr. María Guðjónsdóttir, Dean and Professor at the faculty of Food Science and Nutrition at the University of Iceland.
- Dr. Jørgen Lerfall, Dean and Professor in the faculty of Biology and Food Science at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology
- Dr. Panagiotis Tsakanikas, Research Associate at the department of Food Science & Human Nutrition at Agricultural University of Athens

Members of the Icelandic cod value chain also participated in the interviews (Appendix 11.2). In particular, stakeholders from companies Brim and Lysi were interviewed and asked about their expectations on the VideometerLite instrument. They will be kept anonymized for the scope of this deliverable and are listed as follows:

- Participant 1, Plant Manager at Lysi
- Participant 2, Quality Manager at Lysi
- Participant 3, Director at Brim
- Participant 4, Director at Brim

Results from the above-mentioned interviews showed that participants were initially interested in analyzing different features in seafood, which require specific wavelengths for visualization. Table 1 summarizes the findings.

The wavelengths necessary for the seafood applications were investigated, both by interviewing the TraceMyFish partners and stakeholders, and by performing some in-house tests.

Table 1 Applications and Relative Wavelengths

Feature	Spectrum	Wavelengths in VideometerLite
Fillet color	Visible spectrum	460 nm, 525 nm, 590 nm, 621 nm, 660 nm
Moisture	NIR	850nm
Microbiological spoilage	Whole spectrum	405 nm, 460 nm, 525 nm, 590 nm, 621 nm, 660 nm, and 850 nm
Presence of viscera	Whole spectrum	405 nm, 460 nm, 525 nm, 590 nm, 621 nm, 660 nm, and 850 nm
Presence of parasites	Blue, UV/Fluorescence	405 nm, 460 nm, 525nm
Presence of bones	Whole spectrum	405 nm, 460 nm, 525 nm, 590 nm, 621 nm, 660 nm, and 850 nm
Presence of blood stains	Visible spectrum	460 nm, 525 nm, 590 nm, 621 nm, 660 nm

With the finalization of this stage, after February 2022, three VideometerLites were respectively sent to the partnered universities, where the first round of user tests begun.

6 USER TESTING

In compliance with Pilot Task 6.1, University of Iceland, Agricultural University of Athens and Norwegian University of Science and Technology all received the first version of the VideometerLite instrument in early spring 2022.

After having installed the instrument, testing begun on the first batches of fish samples. During this process, users assessed the use and functionality of the VideometerLite, developing impressions on their user experience (UX) as a whole.

Two semi-structured interviews and a focus group workshop were held in order to collect user feedback, so to plan and structure the 2nd iteration of the development process while satisfying user needs.

6.1 SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

The two interviews (Appendix 11.3) were held via Microsoft Teams calls in May 2022 with:

- Dr. María Guðjónsdóttir, Dean and Professor at the faculty of Food Science and Nutrition at the University of Iceland.
- Dr. Anastasia Lytou, Research Fellow at the department of Department of Food Science & Human Nutrition at Agricultural University of Athens.

Findings from the interviews showed an overall positive perception of the instrument. Both users believed that the instrument was intuitive and easy-to-use with little to no previous training, in particular, because of the easily accessible information on the instrument's User Manual and the helpful customer support. Dr. Lytou, additionally added that she perceived the analysis to be rapid and efficient, explaining that, for each sample, it took approximately 30 seconds to capture its image, process it and save it.

Dr. Guðjónsdóttir was particularly satisfied with the instruments visible spectrum's wavelengths, which allow the visualization of many quality parameters within seafood applications. However, she pointed out the need for UV and NIR wavelength expansion for applications such as moisture and parasite detection. In this regard, Dr. Lytou proposed the customization of wavelengths based on the foodstuff being analyzed.

Finally, the two users expressed their perceptions concerning the mechanical design of the instrument. Both were positive about the portability and wirelessness of the instrument, as these features bring value to users who need to carry the instrument in field. Furthermore, Dr. Lytou reflected on the addition of an incorporated monitor to show when the image is being taken, or alternatively a smartphone VideometerLab Software application to aid in-field analysis.

6.2 FOCUS GROUP WORKSHOP

The focus group workshop was held in November 2022 during the first plenary meeting in Athens, Greece. Four Videometer representatives were present: Dr. Jens Michael Carstensen (CEO), Dr. Nette Schultz (CINO), Alessia del Genio (Marketing Specialist) and Aske Schultz Carstensen (Product Developer).

The aim of the workshop was to:

1. Collect ideas on how the sample should be represented in different applications.
2. Understand and investigate the challenges there are in different applications.
3. Gather ideas for VideometerLite add-ons.

The workshop was moderated by Dr. Nette Schultz and Product Developer, Aske Schultz Carstensen. The two divided the participants into two groups and asked each group to discuss their ideas for 10 minutes.

The attendees and respondents included:

Table 2 Workshop Participants

Name	Role	Company/Institution
Panagiotis Zervas	COO	SCiO Systems
Antonis Koukourikos	CSO	SCiO Systems
Pythagoras Karampiperis	CEO	SCiO Systems
Jørgen Lerfall	Head of Food Science Division, Professor	NTNU
Anita Nordeng Jakobsen	Associate Professor	NTNU
George-John Nychas	Professor Emeritus	AUA
Panagiotis Tsakanikas	Research Associate	AUA
Anastasia Lytou	Research Fellow	AUA
Lemonia Fengou	Research Fellow	AUA

Anastasios Stamatou	Research Associate	AUA
Nikos Chorianopoulos	Research Associate	AUA
Maria Guðjónsdóttir	Faculty Dean, Professor	UoI
Andrea Rakeł Sigurðardóttir	Ph.D. Student	UoI
Hildur Inga Sveinsdóttir	Project Manager, Adjunct Professor	Matis, UoI
Jens Michael Carstensen	CEO	Videometer
Alessia del Genio	Marketing Specialist	Videometer

Inspiration questions were set on the projector, so to help the participants with their idea generation. The questions included were:

1. How can the sample be represented in the most informative way?
2. What kind of measurement error could be introduced and how can it be avoided?
3. How can the instrument be cleaned; in the case it gets dirty?
4. How can instrument ergonomics be improved if they create issues for use?

The moderators did not interrupt the flow of ideas, to control any bias that may occur. After the brainstorming session, each group had 5 minutes to present their ideas. At the end of the workshop, Nette Schultz held a in plenum summary.

Different ideas and opinions came to light. One common issue that emerged was the difficulty in controlling the height of the instrument, so to avoid “light pollution” within the image of a given sample. In fact, participants expressed difficulty in placing the instrument directly on seafood samples, as this can present hygiene related issues. Because of this, they communicated the need for a sort of add-on that could control the distance between the sample and the instrument.

Some of the participants, explored the idea of an add-on, which could aid in the measurement of liquid samples. Said fixture, could hold small rectangular vials and measure color changes, turbidity, and stability in seafood by-product such as fish oil.

Further ideas that emerged regarded the need of a platform, tray that could aid with capturing images of bigger samples, in order not to lose track of the areas captured. Alternatively, they expressed the need for a

rectangular or quadratic opening on the instrument, so not to miss or measure multiple times any area of the larger samples, as this could negatively influence the analysis.

7 SECOND ITERATION

Once feedback was received, the Videometer team, begun the assessment of user needs and requirements that emerged during their first trial and testing processes. Therefore, for the second iteration, development occurred in all aspects of the instrument's and software's architecture and design.

7.1 HARDWARE, OPTICS AND MECHANICS

In light of the applications mentioned by the partnered universities, it was decided to add more powerful LEDs to the VideometerLite instrument. Said LEDs would be suitable for the expansion of UV wavelengths to 365 nm, and, subsequently, the addition of fluorescence filters for applications such as the detection of parasites within fish fillets.

7.2 SOFTWARE (ICT)

The software connection was optimized in order to enhance the rapidity of the instrument's ability to connect, capture and save images. Computational bottlenecks and small bugs were fixed for enhanced efficiency and finally tested.

7.3 SOFTWARE IMAGE ANALYSIS AND PROCESSING & INTERACTION DESIGN

A role mapping and ownership structure was developed as the initial step in the cloud integration. Said systems were put in place to give users access to their workspaces at owner level, write level or read only level.

Cloud integration with the Videometer Cloud Workspaces was made available for the saving and sharing of all analyses results. Furthermore, the possibility to save compressed images in HIPS format was added to the Videometer Cloud Workspaces, allowing users to work on the same images remotely.

Statistics on use and storage space were added to the Cloud Workspaces, in order for users to be aware of their usage of the libraries.

Finally, publicly available workspaces were developed for all users to be able to access Videometer materials and learning resources.

7.4 USERS

The second iteration of user testing will commence in Month 16 (February 2023), after partnered universities will have received their updated prototype of the VideometerLite instrument. Agreements between partnered universities were in relation to testing during the unfolding of Work Package 6 (Piloting and Evaluation). It was decided to perform experiments on the freshness of fish samples, by capturing images of e.g. eyes and gills. During these trials, researchers will be able to explore the use of spectral imaging and the VideometerLite instrument for this application. Final results will be shared at the completion of the TraceMyFish project, in Month 24 (November 2023).

8 USE AND APPLICATIONS

8.1 USE

As seen in Figure 5 and Figure 6 the instrument presents:

- A modular handle, which can be added or removed based on the use (in-field or in-lab).
- An ethernet cable entrance, to connect the device to its relative PC.
- A power bank entrance and power bank to power the instrument.
- Button A (Red LED) to power on/off the instrument.
- Button B (Blue LED) to capture images.

Figure 5 VideometerLite Top

Figure 6 VideometerLite Side

8.1.1 How to power-on, connect over ethernet to PC, take an image and power-off

1. Connect your laptop to the VideometerLite with the ethernet cable. When connecting for the first time, make sure you are using the ethernet cable connection.
2. Connect the power-bank to the VideometerLite. When first connecting the power-bank with the VideometerLite, the device will automatically power-on on its own.
3. If the power-bank has been previously inserted in the VideometerLite, press Button A (power on/off) to power on the device.

4. Once Button B (capture image) is emitting blue light, the VideometerLite is ready for connection and image acquisition.
5. Open the VideometerLab Software. Click on “Imaging Devices”, “VideometerLite”, “Connect” (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Connect to VideometerLite from VideometerLab Software

6. A new window will open. Click on the VideometerLite with wired connection (Figure 8). Click “Connect”.

Figure 8 Connect to VideometerLite

7. Your VideometerLite will be now connected to the VideometerLab Software.
8. To capture an image, click on “Imaging Devices”, “VideometerLite”, “Capture Corrected Image” (Figure 9). Alternatively, press on Button B (Capture Image) or on the F12 key on your keyboard.
9. To disconnect the VideometerLite from the VideometerLab Software, click on “Imaging Devices”, “VideometerLite”, “Disconnect” (Figure 10).

- To power off the VideometerLite, press on Button A (power on/off) until the red LED stops blinking. Once the light will have stopped, your VideometerLite will be off.

Figure 10 Capture Image

Figure 9 Disconnect

8.1.2 Connect to VideometerLite Hotspot

- Power on your device.
- Connect to VideometerLite hotspot by clicking on the PC's Wi-Fi Tab. The hotspot name is the same as the VideometerLite's serial number: LITExxxxxxx.
- You will receive the password in the Set-up File.
- Open the VideometerLab Software. Click on "Imaging Devices", "VideometerLite", "Connect" (Figure 7).
- A new window will open. Click on the VideometerLite with wireless connection (Figure 8). Click "Connect".

8.1.3 Calibrate your VideometerLite

- Power on your device.
- Open the white calibration plate and place the VideometerLite on top of the plate.
- Use the lid from the calibration plate to level out the VideometerLite (Figure 11).

Figure 11 VideometerLite Calibration

4. Hold Button B (Capture Image) for 5 seconds (Figure 5).
5. During the calibration Button B (Capture Image) will blink with a blue light. Once the blue light is constant, the calibration will be done.

8.1.4 How to connect the VideometerLite to a new Wi-Fi.

1. Connect the VideometerLite to your PC either with the ethernet cable or with Wi-Fi connection.
2. Connect your PC to the Wi-Fi you wish to connect your VideometerLite to.
3. Open the VideometerLab Software and click on “Imaging Devices”, “VideometerLite”, “Connect” (Figure 7).
4. Press on “Configure VideometerLite Wi-Fi” (Figure 12).
5. Insert your Wi-Fi password, then press on “Setup and Connect” (Figure 6). You will be now connected to a new Wi-Fi.

Figure 12 Wi-Fi Setup

8.2 APPLICATIONS

During the first TraceMyFish Consortium plenary meeting in Athens, Greece, Videometer representative Dr. Jens Michael Carstensen, demonstrated the use of VideometerLite gathered data and Videometer Cloud Workspaces for colony counting. He illustrated how to utilize the Transformation Builder, Segmentation Builder and Blob Tool to process and analyze the data.

Images were provided by partner Agricultural University of Athens and included total mesophilic cultures of marine origin microorganisms on marine ager.

1. Connect VideometerLite to VideometerLab Software and capture image as described in 8.1, or click on “File”, “MyVideometer Library”, select the image you want to open and click on “Save and Open”. Make sure you are logged in and working in the preferred workspace.
2. Select the Brush Tool and the color for the Active Layer you will use for your colonies. Paint the colonies making sure you include all shades of pixels inside the colonies and that you do not exceed their borders. Select a second color for the Active Layer you will use for the background. Paint the background including all shades of it and making sure you do not include any colonies.
3. Click on “MSI”, “Transformation Builder” and choose “NCDA” for your method. Select the layers you would like to discriminate from each other. Click “Calculate” and then “Apply”.
4. Once you are satisfied with the nCDA, click on the “Save” icon. The Save File window will pop up. Enter the preferred name of your transformation and save it on your desired workspace. You will need this in further steps of the process.
5. Now you can begin performing your segmentation. Click on “MSI”, “Segmentation Builder 2” and select “Pre-Segmentation”. Select “Petri Dish Segmentation”, “Automatic”.
6. Select “Foreground/Background Segmentation” and subsequently “Transformation Based Segmentation”. Adjust any values as needed. If foreground and background are inverted select “Less” in the compare dropdown, instead of the default “Greater”. Click on the “...” icon and select the previously made transformation.
7. Select “Fill holes”, select your preferred unit of measurement and input a value for your preferred “Fill Area Limit” to cover the noise pixels you do not want to include in your segmentation.
8. Select “Separate Touching Objects”. You can initially select “Adaptive”. If you are satisfied with the separation, please continue with the steps, otherwise select “Fixed”. If you have selected “Fixed”, choose “Learn from Image” and adjust the “H-Domes Value (pixels)” and “H-Domes Threshold (pixels)” until satisfied with the separation.
9. Click “Apply”, making sure you have selected the initial image. A new segmentation image will open. If you are satisfied, continue with the process, otherwise go back to any of the previous steps to adjust.
10. Click on the “Mask” Icon and select “From Open Image Masking” and select your final Segmentation as a mask. Make sure you have selected the initial image you started from as the image to be masked (Figure 13).
11. Now, click on “Blobs” and subsequently on “Blob Tool”. The Blob Tool Window will pop-up. Click on the “Blob Collection” text at the top of the window and select extract from image and select your Masked Image (Figure 14).

- You will now be able to view a count of all your colonies and sort them based on area, width, length, compactness and more features (Figure 14).

Figure 13 Image of Segmented Colonies

Figure 14 Colony Count Sorted by Circularity

9 CONCLUSIONS

The VideometerLite instrument is a portable, wireless, easy-to-use and cost-efficient spectral imaging device. Its technology is based on Videometer's LED-based sequential strobing. It was developed with the customer in mind and, therefore, its design process included both technical players and real-life users, who tested and experimented with its functionalities.

The instrument has so far been assessed as being rapid and easy-to-use. Its portability was perceived as a value-adding feature and the spectral imaging technology as innovative and valuable for a wide range of application within the seafood industry.

During the second iteration of the process, UV wavelengths were extended to 365 nm, and fluorescence filters added, allowing for further possibilities within the industry.

Further testing will be brought out, in order to assess not only the new wavelengths including fluorescence filters, but also additional functionalities in the mechanic design and software and cloud architecture. Experiments will be conducted on fish eyes and gills to explore the use of the VideometerLite's spectral imaging and cloud-based technology for seafood freshness.

Furthermore, the VideometerLite has been tested and used for microbiological applications such as colony counting. In this case, it demonstrated to be quite precise and to be able to accurately segment, sort and count colonies.

10 REFERENCES

Carstensen, J.M., (2018). *LED spectral imaging with food and agricultural applications*, Image Sensing Technologies: Materials, Devices, Systems, and Applications V, 1065604, <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2304698>

Carstensen, J.M., Folm-Hansen, J. (2006). *Apparatus and Method of Recording an Image of an Object*, (U.S. Patent No. 7,119,930 B1). U.S. Patent and Trademark Office. <https://videometer.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/VideometerLab-Patent.pdf>

11 APPENDIXES

11.1 INTERVIEW TEMPLATE WITH TMF CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

Introduction:

Aim: creating trust between interviewer and interviewee.

Who am I: Alessia – Digital Marketing Specialist – Videometer A/S

Scope: Understanding their needs in regard to TMF project and VideometerLite

Confidentiality

Introduction questions:

Aim: understanding the context and building the user persona's context.

Name:

What precisely is your role at WORKPLACE?

What do you do on a daily basis?

What skills are required for this job?

Do you work with others?

What instruments do you use?

Which one do you like the most and why?

Which one do you like the least and why?

Current methodologies:

Aim: understanding user persona's needs and feelings.

How do you assess fish traceability/quality, at the moment?

What are the most important features?

Can you describe the process?

Do you have any standards and regulations?

What are the most important ones?

How do you get samples? How do you prepare them before analysis, if you do so?

Do you have any limitations?

Why do you think you have these limitations?

Do you have any evidence or examples of limitations?

Could you rank them from most problematic to least problematic?

What works well with the current process?

Could you provide examples?

Could you rank these from most useful to least?

Are you going to share data with stakeholders? Why do you need to share data?

What are the data sharing processes at the moment? Can you describe them? (N.B. Make sure they touch upon automation and manual labor)

At the moment, are there problems with data sharing? Why? Can you give an example?

How do you think these problems could be solved?

How often do you share data with your stakeholders, at the moment? How often do you expect to share data?

What kind of data do you share with your stakeholders?

Do you organize your data, at the moment? How? Are there problems with this structure? Why? Can you give examples?

Can you explain your security protocols?

Do you use Wi-Fi or ethernet connection?

Expectations:

Aim: understanding user persona's feelings and use cases for scenarios, storyboards, and UMLs.

What is your expected use of the VideometerLite?

You have a VideometerLab and you've heard about the VideometerLite – what differences do you expect to encounter?

Do you believe you will use the instrument as portable or as stationary? Do you expect to use the VMLite without the aid of a computer (as standalone)?

How do you expect to take images of the fish?

What do you want to look at specifically in the fish? (What is more important to look at for traceability)

Is there anything interesting to visualize for fish traceability? How do you visualize that?

How do you expect to use the software?

How do you expect to share the data you gathered with VMLite with the fish value chain to enhance traceability?

How do you expect to save and then visualize the data?

I'm going to list some features. State which ones you are willing to put more effort for:

1. Sharing of your personal data with Videometer?
2. Learning how to use software?
3. Taking courses for software and hardware use?

I'm going to list some features from the VMLite hardware. State which ones sound more appealing for your work:

1. Portability

2. Wireless
3. Cost
4. Ease of use
5. Spectral Imaging Technology

What goals do you have for the use of this instrument in your daily work?

Expansion

Aim: give possibility to add more that may not have been touched upon

11.2 INTERVIEW TEMPLATE WITH ICELANDIC FISHING INDUSTRY

- Which are the most significant pain points in your company's value chain?
- How does your company deal with them?
- What are the most common reasons for complaints?
- Please, describe your company's routines
- Which technology and management system does your company use?
- Does your company use any on-line/at-line sensors?
- What kind of information is connected to your batch/lot?
- Which hazards are most challenging in your value chain?
- Where do you see potential for improvements?
- Are there significant bottlenecks in your current system?

11.3 USER FEEDBACK INTERVIEW TEMPLATES

Do you have any input for improvement?

Effectiveness:

- Can you assess how you find all the information you need?
- Can you assess how it is to carry out your activities with the VideometerLite?

Efficiency:

- Can you sustain a high level of productivity while using the instrument?

Safety:

- If you make mistakes, can you assess how it is to recover from them?

Utility:

- Can you assess the functions of the product?

- Can you assess if you can carry-out all your tasks as you would like to with the product?

Learning:

- Can you assess if the interface allows for you to explore the instrument?
- Do you feel confident exploring the product?
- Do you feel like you have learnt all the functions?
- Can you assess the difficulty?

Any other feedback?